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UDC 336

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Functional and organizational mechanism of insurance of financial risks in banking activities

The subject of the research is the theoretical and practical aspects of the functional and organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking.

The aim of the research is to determine the essence of the functional-organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking, types of financial risk insurance in banking, and factors influencing the functional-organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking.

Research methods. When writing the article, general scientific and special methods, methods of analysis and synthesis, graphic and tabular method were used.

Results of the investigation. As a result of writing the article, it was established that the relevance of the issue of financial risk insurance in the context of the banking sector includes the following aspects: a general approach to financial risk insurance; determination of financial and credit risk insurance; components of financial risk insurance; specifics of financial risk insurance. It was determined that the functional-organizational mechanism of insurance of financial risks in banking is a multifaceted

phenomenon, which is considered by many scientists as a fundamental basis in the management and insurance of financial risks in the entire banking sector. This is justified by the fact that financial risks are associated with possible losses of financial resources, where the insurance of financial and credit risks is understood as a mechanism that aims to protect the property interests of the insured against possible losses arising from non-fulfillment or improper fulfillment by counterparties of their financial obligations Yazan under contracts.

Scope of the results. Finance, Economics, Risk Management, Banking.

Conclusions. It is proved that according to the functional and organizational mechanism of insurance of financial risks in banking includes various elements, processes and influencing factors aimed at effective management and reduction of financial risks that may arise due to various circumstances. Among the main components of the functional and organizational mechanism of insurance of financial risks in banking activity, the following are defined: risk analysis; insurance policy formation; selection of insurance products; internal control processes; portfolio management strategies; insurance reserves; staff training and development.

Keywords: functional and organizational mechanism, insurance of financial risks, banking institutions, influencing factors, types of insurance.

РУСІНА Ю. О.

Функціонально–організаційний механізм страхування фінансових ризиків в банківській діяльності

Предметом дослідження є теоретико–практичні аспекти функціонально–організаційного механізму страхування фінансових ризиків в банківській діяльності.

Метою дослідження є визначення сутності функціонально–організаційного механізму страхування фінансових ризиків в банківській діяльності, видів страхування фінансових ризиків в банківській діяльності та чинників впливу на функціонально–організаційний механізм страхування фінансових ризиків у банківській діяльності.

Методи дослідження. При написанні статті було використано загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи, методи аналізу та синтезу, графічно–табличний метод.

Результати роботи. В результаті написання статті встановлено, що актуальність питання щодо страхування фінансових ризиків у контексті банківської сфери включає такі аспекти: загальний підхід до страхування фінансових ризиків; визначення страхування фінансово–кредитних ризиків; складові страхування фінансових ризиків; специфіка страхування фінансових ризиків. Визначено, що функціонально–організаційний механізм страхування фінансових ризиків в банківській діяльності це багатоаспектне явище, яке розглядається як фундаментальна основа в управлінні та страхуванні фінансових ризиків в усій банківській сфері.

Галузь застосування результатів. Фінанси, економіка, ризик–менеджмент, банківська справа.

Висновки. Доведено, що функціонально–організаційний механізм страхування фінансових ризиків у банківській діяльності включає в себе різні елементи, процеси та чинники впливу, які спрямовані на ефективне управління та зменшення фінансових ризиків, що можуть виникнути внаслідок різних обставин. Серед основних складових функціонально–організаційного механізму страхування фінансових ризиків у банківській діяльності визначено: аналіз ризиків; формування політики страхування; вибір страхових продуктів; внутрішні процеси контролю; стратегії управління портфелем; страхові резерви; навчання та розвиток персоналу.

Ключові слова: функціонально–організаційний механізм, страхування фінансових ризиків, банківські установи, чинники впливу, види страхування.

Formulation of the problem. Financial risk insurance in banking is an important practice for reducing possible losses and ensuring the stability of financial institutions. The relevance of the issue of financial and credit risk insurance in the context of the banking and financial sphere includes the following aspects: a general approach to financial risk insurance; determination of financial and credit risk

insurance; division of insurance into credit and financial risks; components of financial risk insurance; specifics of financial risk insurance. The functional–organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking is a multifaceted phenomenon, which is considered by many scientists as a fundamental basis in the management and insurance of financial risks in the entire banking sector. This is justified by the fact that financial and credit risks are associated with possible losses of financial resources, where financial and credit risk insurance is understood as a mechanism that aims to protect the property interests of the insured against possible losses arising from non–fulfillment or improper fulfillment by counterparties of their financial contractual obligations [1; 3; 7; 10].

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. Some scholars consider insurance and financial risk management as an understanding that insurance can be used to protect against various risks in the financial sector and banking, among such scholars: V. D. Bazylevych, F. A. Vazhynskiy, K. A. Herasymov, B. M. Hnatkivskiy, P. A. Horyslavets, N. P. Dubrova, L. M. Yeris, O. V. Zaitsev, S. V. Zemliachov, M. V. Kamen-skykh, O. A. Kyrychenko, O. I. Kirieiev, A. M. Kobylin, V. V. Kovalenko, O. I. Kolobov, O. V. Krukhmal, A. Yu. Marchenko, L. V. Moroz, O. P. Pavlenko, O. I. Petryk, N. P. Pohorieltseva, A. Yu. Roskina, R. V. Semmentsov, I. B. Khoma and others.

Presenting main material. Financial risk insurance in banking is an important aspect of risk management in which banking institutions face various financial challenges, and insurance can be

one of those tools to help reduce possible losses. The functional and organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking may include the following types of financial risk insurance (Table 1):

These types of financial risk insurance allow banks to be more resilient in the face of financial fluctuations and ensure stability in their financial portfolio. Let’s consider them in more detail [5; 8; 11; 15].

1. Credit risk insurance is a security measure for cases when a banking institution cannot pay its credit obligations. This allows you to insure yourself against possible financial losses in the event of the borrower’s insolvency. Usually, the agreement provides for the payment of an insurance indemnity in the event of bankruptcy, non–payment or other situations where the debtor cannot fulfill his financial obligations. This type of insurance allows maintaining economic stability and stimulates credit agreements. If it were not possible to insure credit risk, then banking institutions would refrain from providing financial assistance due to the risk of financial losses.

2. Interest rate risk insurance is a type of financial protection that is provided in case of financial losses associated with changes in the level of interest rates. This can apply to both financial institutions and other entities that deal with variable interest rates.

3. Interest rate hedging is a complex financial arrangement and can be used to reduce financial fluctuations associated with changes in market interest rates. Hedging the risk of currency fluctuations is one of the methods that allow banking institutions to reduce the impact of negative changes in exchange

Table 1. Types of financial risk insurance in banking [2; 4; 6; 12]

	Type of insurance	Characteristic
1	Credit risk insurance	Banks can enter into agreements with insurance companies to protect borrowers against insolvency. This can be especially important when working with large corporate clients.
2	Interest rate risk insurance	Changes in the level of interest rates can affect the bank’s profit. Insurance can help reduce the losses associated with uncertainty in this matter.
3	Insurance of the risk of currency fluctuations	Banks operating on an international scale may face the risk of exchange rate fluctuations. Insurance can help protect them against losses related to changes in exchange rates.
4	Operational risk insurance	This type of insurance includes risks associated with inefficient or defective activities, technical problems, fraud, etc.
5	Liquidity risk insurance	Banks can enter into agreements to receive financial assistance in case of liquidity problems.
6	Legal and regulatory risk	Associated with the possibility of losses or failure arising from non–compliance of banking activity with the requirements of legislation and regulatory standards. This may include the risk of violating the laws, regulations and legal acts that govern the banking sector.

rates on their financial positions. This is a financial instrument that allows you to protect against possible losses associated with changes in exchange rates. The main aspects of currency fluctuation risk insurance: forward and futures contracts – forward contracts allow market participants to protect themselves from exchange rate fluctuations by entering into an agreement to buy or sell a currency at a fixed rate in the future. Futures contracts are similar to forwards, but they are standardized and traded on organized exchanges; options – currency options grant the right, but not the obligation, to buy or sell a currency at a certain price during a certain period; swaps – currency swaps allow you to exchange one currency for another at a fixed rate during a certain period; currency operations in the market – market participants can use various strategies and tech-

niques to manage the risks of currency fluctuations; insurance – some companies use insurance products to protect against currency risk. For example, an insurance policy can be taken out that compensates for losses related to currency fluctuations.

It is important to consider that each of these methods has its advantages and disadvantages, and their choice depends on the specific circumstances and strategic goals of the banking institution. Also, the risk associated with currency transactions is always present, and even insurance means do not guarantee the complete exclusion of possible losses [9; 13; 14].

4. Operational risk insurance is one of the forms of insurance aimed at protecting banking institutions from possible losses associated with incorrect or inefficient operation of operational processes. Op-

Table 2. Factors influencing the functional and organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking [1–5]

	The factor	Sign
1.	Risk assessment	Banks must analyze and evaluate various financial risks that they may face in detail. This includes credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and others
2.	Creation of reserves	Banks establish reserves to cover possible losses associated with various types of risks. These reserves help ensure the bank's financial stability in adverse circumstances
3.	Insurance	Banks can enter into insurance agreements to protect against certain risks. For example, credit default insurance can help reduce losses associated with loan defaults
4.	Portfolio diversification	Asset allocation across different classes and markets can reduce the risk of losses. This strategy allows banks to manage financial risks more effectively
5.	Regulation	Government and banking regulators establish rules and restrictions for risk management. Banks must comply with these regulations to ensure the stability of the financial system
6.	Technological innovations	The use of modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, can facilitate the identification and management of financial risks
7.	Monitoring and analysis	Constant monitoring of market conditions and internal processes allows banks to quickly respond to changes in the financial environment and timely adjust their strategies
8.	Understanding risk	It is important that the enterprise thoroughly understands what risks exist in its field of activity. This means identifying possible sources of risk and their consequences
9.	Risk management	On the basis of risk assessment, risk management strategies should be developed. This may include taking measures to reduce the risk, shifting the risk to another party (eg through insurance) or accepting the risk with full awareness of the consequences
10.	Effectiveness of risk management	It is necessary to develop and improve the risk management system, based on the best international practices and taking into account the specifics of one's own industry and enterprise
11.	Peculiarities of financial risks	Particular attention should be paid to financial risks, such as the risk of changes in interest rates and exchange rates. For this, financial instruments such as derivatives can be used to protect the enterprise from negative changes in these parameters
12.	Information technology	Modern information technologies, in particular data analytics and artificial intelligence, can be useful tools for identifying and analyzing risks
13.	Education and training	Training and professional development of personnel regarding risk management are important for the successful implementation of risk management strategies in the enterprise

erational risk includes the risk of systems failure, fraud, personnel error, changes in legislation and other similar aspects that could lead to losses.

Operational risk insurance can be an important part of a risk management strategy for banking institutions, especially those that depend on complex operational processes and infrastructure. However, it should be noted that insurance is not a one-size-fits-all solution and should be supplemented with other risk management methods.

5. Liquidity risk insurance is a financial mechanism that allows financial institutions and other risk management entities to insure themselves against possible problems related to the lack of cash or other liquid assets to fulfill financial obligations. Consequently, liquidity risk insurance can help management entities better manage their finances, reduce the impact of possible financial difficulties and protect themselves from unforeseen situations related to cash flows.

6. Legal and regulatory risk is an important component for banking institutions and is associated with the possibility of losses or failure arising from non-compliance of banking activities with the requirements of legislation and regulatory standards. This may include the risk of violating the laws, regulations and legal acts that govern the banking sector. Therefore, banks must take care of effective management of these risks by developing and implementing strategies and policies taking into account legal and regulatory requirements. In addition, they must be ready to interact with regulators and timely implement changes in accordance with new requirements and standards. The functional and organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking is quite complex and includes a number of factors that affect it (Table 2):

These factors interact with each other, creating a functional and organizational mechanism for insurance of financial risks in the banking sector.

In general, effective risk management is a necessary condition for the stable and successful operation of any banking institution. It is important to constantly adapt new approaches to risk management, as the market situation and the economic environment are subject to constant changes [5–11].

Conclusions

The functional-organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking includes various

elements, processes and influencing factors aimed at effective management and reduction of financial risks that may arise due to various circumstances. The main components of the functional and organizational mechanism of financial risk insurance in banking include:

1. Risk analysis: the bank determines and evaluates various types of financial risks, such as credit, interest, currency, operational, etc. This includes the study of economic, financial and other factors that may affect the financial condition of the bank.

2. Formation of insurance policy: the bank develops an insurance strategy, determining which risks can be transferred to insurance companies and which should be managed internally.

3. Selection of insurance products: the bank selects insurance products and policies that meet its needs. This may include customer insolvency policies, credit risk insurance, securities portfolio insurance, etc.

4. Internal control processes: the bank implements internal control and monitoring systems to identify possible risk situations. This may include early warning systems, internal control audits and regular risk analyses.

5. Portfolio management strategies: the bank develops portfolio management strategies to reduce risk concentration. This may include diversification of assets, management of loan terms, use of financial instruments to reduce currency risk, etc.

6. Insurance reserves: the bank forms insurance reserves that are used to cover losses that may arise as a result of financial risks.

7. Training and development of personnel: the bank ensures that its personnel are well-versed in risk management issues and can effectively interact with insurance companies. Together, these elements constitute a functional and organizational mechanism that allows banks to effectively manage and reduce financial risks in their activities, since the management and insurance of financial risks is an important part of the activities of banking institutions to ensure their stability and reliability [7–15].

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